

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Supplementary Figure S1. Fungal maximum likelihood concatenated phylogenetic tree from a 1478 bp matrix (676 bp nrDNA ITS, 398 bp TEF, and 581 bp TUB). Bootstrap values were calculated with 2000 iterations.

Supplementary Figure S2. Sequence accumulation curves for the prokaryotic metagenomic reads dataset. Groups were chosen based on the confidence intervals. Solid lines indicate interpolated data, and dashed lines indicate the extrapolation (prediction). Curves are by isolate (A), fungal order (B), and fungal family (C).

Supplementary Figure S3. Sequence accumulation curves for bacteria from the metagenomic contig data. Groups were chosen based on the confidence intervals. Solid lines indicate interpolated data, and dashed lines indicate the extrapolation (prediction). Curves are by isolate (A), fungal order (B), and fungal family (C).

Supplementary Figure S4. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) for bacteria from the full metagenomic contig dataset. 2-Dimensional solution with a stress value = 0.0838. Visualizations are by fungal order (A) and fungal family (B).

Supplementary Figure S5. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) for the bacterial domain from the balanced metagenomic contig dataset. 2-Dimensional solution with a stress value = 0.0829. Visualizations are by fungal order (A) and fungal family (B).

Supplementary Figure S6. Ordinations for the full dataset for prokaryotic communities using read data. **A.** 2-dimensional NMDS by fungal orders (stress value 0.0000478). No clear clusters are observed. **B.** NMDS by fungal families. No visible clusters are observed. **C.** dbRDA by fungal order. Visible clusters are observed in the right upper panel for *Diaporthales* and *Glomerellales*. **D.** dbRDA by fungal family. *Glomerellaceae* formed a cluster in the right upper panel. **E.** Procrustes visualization for prokaryotic communities. The test indicates phylogenetic signal (0.042) with a moderate correlation (0.4689).

Supplementary Figure S7. Ordinations for the balanced prokaryotic communities for read data. **A.** 2-dimensional NMDS (stress value 8.06E-05) by fungal orders. No visible clusters were observed. **B.** 2-dimensional NMDS for fungal families. No visible clusters were observed. **C.** dbRDA by fungal orders. Visible clusters are observed for the three most represented orders. **D.** dbRDA by fungal families. Visible clusters are observed for the three best-represented families. **E.** Procrustes test for the prokaryotic balanced dataset. The test indicates phylogenetic signal (0.001) and a strong correlation for the evaluated models (0.988).

Supplementary Figure S8. Relative abundance of the top 15 most abundant bacterial genera among the fungal isolates for contig (A) and read (B) data. For B, “unid.” means that the taxon was not identified at the genus level. The Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree was constructed using concatenated nrDNA ITS, TEF, and TUB sequences. Bootstrap values are shown on nodes.

Supplementary Figure S9. Multinomial classification plots for *Amphisphaeriales* and *Glomerellales* comparison for bacteria for contig data. Classification by order (A), family (B), and genus (C).

Supplementary Figure S10. Multinomial classification plots for *Diaporthales* and *Glomerellales* comparison for bacteria for contig data. Classification by order (A), family (B), and genus (C).

Supplementary Figure S11. Multinomial classification plots for *Amphisphaerales* and *Diaportheales* comparison for bacteria for contig data. Classification by order (A), family (B), and genus (C).

Supplementary Figure S12. Procrustes plots built with the superimposition of NMDS and dbRDA scores for each contig dataset. **A.** Bacterial metagenomic data, correlation 0.4689, significance 0.042, 999 permutations. Visibly, samples M22, K02 and K21 are contributing with the reduction of significance. **B.** Viral metagenomic data, correlation 0.9431, significance 0.001, 999 permutations. **C.** Viral metatranscriptomic data, correlation 0.8033, significance 0.001, 999 permutations.

Supplementary Figure S13. Sequence accumulation curves for the viral metagenomic dataset by reads. Groups were chosen based on the confidence intervals. Solid lines indicate interpolated data, and dashed lines indicate the extrapolation (prediction). Curves are by isolate (A), fungal order (B), and fungal family (C).

Supplementary Figure S14. Sequence accumulation curves for viruses from metagenomic contig data. Groups were chosen based on the confidence intervals. Solid lines indicate interpolated data and dashed lines the extrapolation (prediction). Curves are by fungal isolate (A), order (B), and family (C).

Supplementary Figure S15. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) for the viral metagenomic contig dataset. **A** and **B** correspond to the full dataset; 2-Dimensional solution retrieved with a stress value = 0.0956. Samples colored by fungal order (A) and family (B). Samples K21, M27 and M67 were visibly scattered from the main cluster of samples. **C** and **D** correspond to the balanced dataset, reporting a stress value = 0.0607. **C**. Balanced NMDS colored by fungal order. Sample M27 appeared in a different quadrant from the rest of the *Glomerellales*. Sample M1b appears closer to the *Amphisphaeriales* than to the *Diaporthales*. **D**. NMDS colored by family. Consistent cluster for the samples inside the *Pestalotiopsidaceae* (*Amphisphaeriales*) is being displayed, in contrast with *Diaporthaceae* and *Glomerellaceae* with at least one sample distant from its main conglomerate.

Supplementary Figure S16. Ordinations for the viral metagenomic full dataset by reads. **A.** 2-dimensional NMDS by fungal order (stress value $8.34E-05$). No visible orders were observed. **B.** 2-dimensional NMDS by fungal family. No visible clusters were observed. **C.** dbRDA by fungal order. Clusters for *Amphisphaeriales*, *Diaporthales*, and *Glomerellales* were observed in the right panel. **D.** dbRDA by fungal family. One cluster grouping members of the *Diaporthaceae* and *Glomerellaceae* were observed in the upper right panel, while members of *Pestalotiopsidaceae* were visibly clustered at the bottom of the right panel. **E.** Procrustes for the viral metagenomic full dataset by reads. Phylogenetic signal was detected (0.025) with a good correlation of the models (0.6974).

Supplementary Figure S17. Ordinations for the viral metagenomic balanced dataset by reads. **A.** 2-dimensional NMDS by fungal order (stress value 8.01E-05). No visible orders were observed. **B.** 2-dimensional NMDS by fungal family. No visible clusters were observed. **C.** dbRDA by fungal order. Clusters for *Amphisphaerales*, *Diaporthales*, and *Glomerellales* were observed. **D.** dbRDA by fungal family. Clusters with samples from each family were observed. **E.** Procrustes for the viral metagenomic balanced dataset by reads. Phylogenetic signal was detected (0.001) with a strong correlation of the models (0.991).

Supplementary Figure S18. Multinomial classification plots for *Amphisphaerales* and *Diaporthales* comparison for viral metagenomic contig data. Classification by viral realm (A), kingdom (B), and class (C).

Supplementary Figure S19. Multinomial classification for *Diaporthales* and *Glomerellales* comparison for viral metagenomic contig data. Classification by viral realm (A), kingdom (B), and class (C).

Supplementary Figure S20. Multinomial classification for *Amphisphaeriales* and *Glomerellales* comparison for viral metagenomic contig data. Classification by viral realm (A), kingdom (B), and class (C).

Supplementary Figure S21. Sequence accumulation curves for the viral metatranscriptomic read dataset. Groups were chosen based on the confidence intervals. Solid lines indicate interpolated data and dashed lines the extrapolation (prediction). Curves are by fungal isolate (A), order (B), and family (C).

Supplementary Figure S22. Sequence accumulation curves for viruses from metatranscriptomic contig data. Groups were chosen based on the confidence intervals. Solid lines indicate interpolated data and dashed lines the extrapolation (prediction). Curves are by fungal isolate (A), order (B), and family (C).

Supplementary Figure S23. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) for the metatranscriptome viral domain using contig data. **A** and **B** correspond to the full dataset; 2-Dimensional solution retrieved with a stress value = 0.0902. **A.** Samples colored by fungal order, from all the groups, only *Amphisphaeriales* seems to be clustering. **B.** Samples colored by family. The *Diaporthaceae* appeared to form two groups, while sample M5t (*Xylariales inc. sed.*) and K21 (*Botryosphaeriaceae*) were clustered despite belonging to different groups. **C** and **D** correspond to the balanced dataset, reporting a stress value = 0.0621. **C.** Balanced NMDS colored by fungal order. The distance among some samples in *Amphisphaeriales*, *Diaporthales*, and *Glomerellales* becomes visible in the upper left quadrant. **D.** NMDS colored by family. Samples from the three different families seem to repeat the pattern observed for the balanced metagenome data. Some samples like M1b and M20 (*Diaporthaceae*) seemed to form a cluster while the other two members of this family are being displayed in another quadrant.

Supplementary Figure S24. 3-dimensional NMDS (stress value $8.10E-02$) for the full metatranscriptomic viral read dataset by fungal orders. **A.** Dimensions 1 and 2 without clear groupings. **B.** Dimensions 1 and 3, three samples in *Diaporthales* appear to be grouped at the bottom. **C.** Dimensions 2 and 3, with visible formed clusters for *Amphisphaeriales*, *Diaporthales*, and *Glomerellales*.

Supplementary Figure S25. 3-dimensional NMDs for the full metatranscriptomic viral read dataset by fungal families. **A.** Dimensions 1 and 2 without clear groupings. **B.** Dimensions 1 and 3 without clear clusterings. **C.** Dimensions 2 and 3 with visible clusters for *Diaporthace*, *Glomerellaceae*, and *Pestalotiopsidaceae* formed.

Supplementary Figure S26. Ordinations for the full metatranscriptomic viral read dataset. **A.** dbRDA by fungal orders. Three samples from *Diaporthales* and *Glomerellales* are grouped near the center and left panel. **B.** dbRDA by fungal families. Only three samples from *Glomerellaceae* appear to be grouped. **C.** Procrustes visualization. The test indicates phylogenetic signal (0.001) with a good correlation for the models (0.7716).

Supplementary Figure S27. Ordinations for the viral metatranscriptomic balanced read dataset. **A.** 2-dimensional NMDS by fungal order (stress value $9.14E-02$). Visible clusters for the best-represented groups were observed. **B.** 2-dimensional NMDS by fungal family. Visible clusters (somewhat linear) were observed. **C.** dbRDA by fungal order. Samples from *Amphisphaeriales* and *Glomerellales* seem to form two clusters. **D.** dbRDA by fungal family. No consolidated clusters for the families were observed. **E.** Procrustes for the viral metatranscriptomic balanced dataset. Phylogenetic signal was detected (0.001) with a strong correlation of the models (0.9689).

Supplementary Figure S28. Multinomial classification for *Diaportheales* and *Glomerellales* comparison for viral metatranscriptomic contig data. Classification by viral realm (A), kingdom (B), and class (C).

Supplementary Figure S29. Multinomial classification for *Amphisphaerales* and *Diaporthales* comparison for viral metatranscriptomic contig data. Classification by viral realm (A), kingdom (B), and class (C).

Supplementary Figure S30. Multinomial classification for *Amphisphaerales* and *Glomerellales* comparison for viral metatranscriptomic contig data. Classification by viral realm (A), kingdom (B), and class (C).